

Synthesis of alkoxyphthalimide derivatives of *p*-bis-(2-hydroxy-4-aryl-6-iminothiazolidino[4,5-*b*]pyrimidin-*N*⁶-yl)biphenyls

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Biphenyl-yl-4,4'-bisthiourea **1** reacts with monochloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate to furnish *p*-bis-(2-iminothiazolidin-4-one-*N*²-yl)biphenyl **2**. Condensation of ω -bromoalkoxyphthalimides **3a-c** with **2** gave corresponding alkoxyphthalimide derivatives **4a-c**. In the compounds **4a-c**, reactive methylene group of thiazolidinone ring at position-5 was condensed with araldehydes **5a-c** to give *p*-bis-(3-*n*-alkoxyphthalimido-5-arylidene-2-iminothiazolidin-4-one-*N*²-yl)biphenyls **6a-i**. The titled compounds **7a-i** were synthesized by cyclisation reaction of the compounds **6a-i** with urea in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in acetic acid medium. In another reaction route, substituted benzaldehydes **5a-c** were reacted first with **2** to give *p*-bis-(5-arylidene-2-iminothiazolidin-4-one-*N*²-yl)biphenyls **8a-c** which could be cyclised with urea to furnish *p*-bis-(2-hydroxy-4-aryl-6-iminothiazolidino[4,5-*b*]pyrimidin-*N*⁶-yl)biphenyls **9a-c**. The compounds **6a-i** and **7a-i** were also synthesized by condensation reactions of **8a-c** and **9a-c** with **3a-c** respectively.

In continuation of our efforts for synthesizing oxygen substituted hydroxylamines including imidoxy¹ (phthalimidoxy, succinimidoxy, benzhydroximidoxy), amino-oxy² and biguanidino-oxy³ derivatives of aliphatic and heterocyclic compounds, it was planned to synthesize some series of combinational molecules in which thiazolidinone, pyrimidine and alkoxyphthalimide moieties are present. It was also thought that biological activities might be enhanced in target molecules.

Results and discussion

Benzidine dihydrochloride when heated with ammonium thiocyanate in 25% HCl gave biphenyl-yl-4,4'-bisthiourea **1** which on cyclisation with monochloroacetic acid in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in dry ethanol yielded *p*-bis-(2-iminothiazolidin-4-one-*N*²-yl)biphenyl **2**. Formation of compound **2** was confirmed by spectroscopic and chemical methods. The intense IR (potassium bromide) band at 1640 cm⁻¹ showed C=N stretching of imino group attached to thiazolidinone nucleus while the band for ring C=O group appeared at 1692 cm⁻¹ and for ring NH stretching vibrations in the region 3370–3310 cm⁻¹. Lack of absorption band in the region of 2500–2700 cm⁻¹ indicates the absence of carboxyl group that confirms the cyclic structure of compound **2**. Two signals in ¹H NMR (deuteriochloroform) were also observed for protons of NH and methylene group at δ 6.9 and 4.6 ppm respectively as

separate two singlets. The compound **2** also showed the positive tests for carbonyl group and especially for the ketonic group. ω -Bromoalkoxyphthalimides **3a-c** were condensed with **2** in absolute alcohol giving *p*-bis-(3-*n*-alkoxyphthalimido-2-iminothiazolidin-4-one-*N*²-yl)biphenyls **4a-c** using pyridine as base. ω -Bromoalkoxyphthalimides **3a-c** were prepared by reported method⁴. Disappearance of the N-OH group resonance at δ 6.1 ppm of *N*-hydroxyphthalimide and appearance of new resonance for alkyl side chain confirmed the reaction. Condensation of **3a-c** with **2** at the nitrogen atom was confirmed by IR and ¹H NMR spectroscopy. Free NH stretching vibrations for **4a-c** in the region of 3370–3310 cm⁻¹, which were present in its precursor, had disappeared and a strong band in the region of 1300–1160 cm⁻¹ appeared for the new C–N bond. Furthermore, C=O stretching vibrations of thiazolidinone ring was still present in compounds **4a-c** and an additional band for C=O group of alkoxyphthalimide moiety was also observed in the region 1740–1730 cm⁻¹.

The reaction conditions, however, were dependent upon the length of the alkyl chain of the ω -bromoalkoxyphthalimides. Refluxing times for complete reaction varied between 10–22 h. Various bases have been used to eliminate hydrobromic acid generated during course of reaction. Organic bases used in present investigation were pyridine, piperidine, piperazine, trimethylamine and triethylamine.

Table I. Physical and analytical data for compounds 4a-c, 6a-l, 7a-l and 9a-c

Compd.	Reflux (h)	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	Molecular formula	Analysis : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
4a	18	52	298	C ₃₈ H ₂₈ O ₈ N ₆ S ₂	59.62 (60.00)	3.16 3.68	10.87 11.05
4b	20	56	304	C ₄₀ H ₃₂ O ₈ N ₆ S ₂	60.27 (60.91)	3.79 4.06	10.36 10.65
4c	16	58	310	C ₄₃ H ₃₆ O ₈ N ₆ S ₂	61.31 (61.76)	4.03 4.41	9.98 10.29
6a	10	48	280	C ₃₂ H ₃₆ O ₈ N ₆ S ₂	66.28 (66.66)	3.51 3.84	8.67 8.97
6b	11	46	302	C ₅₂ H ₃₆ O ₁₀ N ₆ S ₂	64.09 (64.46)	3.42 3.71	8.34 8.67
6c	12	44	296	C ₅₄ H ₄₀ O ₁₀ N ₆ S ₂	64.82 (65.06)	3.69 4.01	8.21 8.43
6d	11	48	308	C ₅₄ H ₄₀ O ₈ N ₆ S ₂	66.84 (67.21)	3.76 4.14	8.42 8.71
6e	10	42	306	C ₅₄ H ₄₀ O ₁₀ N ₆ S ₂	64.78 (65.06)	3.60 4.01	8.29 8.43
6f	12	49	298	C ₅₆ H ₄₄ O ₁₀ N ₆ S ₂	65.13 (65.62)	4.01 4.29	7.96 8.20
6g	10	47	312	C ₅₆ H ₄₄ O ₈ N ₆ S ₂	67.38 (67.74)	4.06 4.43	8.19 8.46
6h	12	52	320	C ₅₆ H ₄₄ O ₁₀ N ₆ S ₂	65.26 (65.62)	3.97 4.29	7.93 8.20
6i	12	46	312	C ₅₈ H ₄₈ O ₁₀ N ₆ S ₂	65.74 (66.15)	4.21 4.56	7.79 7.98
7a	11	39	270	C ₅₄ H ₃₆ O ₈ N ₁₀ S ₂	63.36 (63.77)	3.23 3.54	13.43 13.77
7b	12	41	282	C ₅₄ H ₃₆ O ₁₀ N ₁₀ S ₂	61.41 (61.83)	3.06 3.43	13.09 13.35
7c	10	39	264	C ₅₆ H ₄₀ O ₁₀ N ₁₀ S ₂	62.02 (62.42)	3.34 3.71	12.73 13.01
7d	10	42	276	C ₅₆ H ₄₀ O ₈ N ₁₀ S ₂	64.01 (64.36)	3.46 3.83	13.06 13.40
7e	12	36	286	C ₅₆ H ₄₀ O ₁₀ N ₁₀ S ₂	62.11 (62.45)	3.39 3.71	12.71 13.01
7f	11	39	268	C ₅₈ H ₄₄ O ₁₀ N ₁₀ S ₂	62.68 (63.04)	3.56 3.98	12.41 12.68
7g	10	43	276	C ₅₈ H ₄₄ O ₈ N ₁₀ S ₂	64.61 (64.92)	3.71 4.10	12.68 13.05
7h	12	44	292	C ₅₈ H ₄₄ O ₁₀ N ₁₀ S ₂	62.69 (63.04)	3.61 3.98	12.39 12.68
7i	11	42	290	C ₆₀ H ₄₈ O ₁₀ N ₁₀ S ₂	63.23 (63.60)	3.91 4.24	12.02 12.36
9a	10	54	335	C ₃₄ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₈ S ₂	63.61 (63.94)	3.09 3.44	17.28 17.55
9b	12	54	340	C ₃₄ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₈ S ₂	64.11 (64.47)	3.01 3.28	16.49 16.71
9c	12	51	318	C ₃₆ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₈ S ₂	65.04 (65.32)	3.43 3.72	15.71 16.04

Inorganic bases like NaOH, KOH, NaH, K₂CO₃, Na₂CO₃ etc. were also tried for forgoing reactions but better yield were obtained when pyridine was used as base. Anhydrous sodium or potassium carbonate gave decomposed products. Sodium hydroxide also decompose the reaction contents and colloidal sulfur was precipitated. Sodium hydride in xylene was used but it gave a mixture of products with more than four tlc spots which could not be separated. Petroleum ether, acetone, acetic acid, ethanol and methanol were used for reaction medium but absolute alcohol provided satisfactory medium.

Compounds 4a-c on reacting with *p*-substituted araldehydes 5a-c in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in acetic acid medium furnished *p*-bis-(3-*n*-alkoxyphthalimido-5-arylidene-2-iminothiazolidin-4-one-*N*²-yl)-biphenyls 6a-l via Claisen condensation. Formation of products was confirmed by spectral data. Stretching vibrations for C=O group of parent thiazolidinone rings (2 and 4a-c) showed a bathochromic shift in carbonyl absorption region (1698–1692 cm⁻¹ to 1682–1678 cm⁻¹) due to unsaturation at position-5 which is conjugated with carbonyl group at position-4 as in the case of 6a-l. The IR band in the

Table 2. Spectroscopic data of compounds 4a-c, 6a-l, 7a-l and 9a-c

Compd.	IR (potassium bromide) cm ⁻¹	¹ H NMR (δ ppm)	MS (<i>m/z</i>)
4a	2910 (C-H), 1738 (C=O, phthalimido group), 1692 (C=O, thiazolidinone ring), 1640 (C=N), 685 (C-S-C)	2.6 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.1 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 4.5 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.6-7.8 (8H, m, ArH)	M ⁺⁺ 760 (62), 380 (40), 190 (100), 114 (74)
4b	3035 (Ar-H), 1735 (C=O), 1698 (C=O), 1595 (C=N), 665 (C-S-C)	2.5 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.8 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.2 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 4.6 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.6-7.9 (8H, m, ArH)	M ⁺⁺ 788 (42), 152 (100), 76 (84)
4c	2925 (C-H), 1732 (C=O), 1696 (C=O), 650 (C-S-C)	2.5 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.6 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.9 (4H, t, NCH ₂), 3.1 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 4.3 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.7-7.9 (8H, m, ArH)	M ⁺⁺ 816 (43), 218 (49), 152 (100), 146 (68), 76 (82)
6a	3040 (C-H), 2860 (N-O), 1700 (C=O), 1682 (C=O), 1642 (C=C)	2.7 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.2 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 6.2 (1H, s, CH), 7.6-7.9 (13H, m, ArH)	M ⁺⁺ 936 (33), 398 (49), 190 (100), 146 (67)
6b	3476 (O-H), 1710 (C=O), 1680 (C=O), 1648 (C=C), 806 (C-H), 671 (C-S-C)	2.8 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.0 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 6.1 (1H, s, CH), 6.3 (1H, br s, OH), 7.7-7.9 (12H, m, ArH)	M ⁺⁺ 968 (36), 782 (46), 190 (100), 152 (58), 146 (72)
6c	3038 (C-H), 2915 (C-H), 1705 (C=O), 1680 (C=O), 660 (C-S-C)	2.9 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.2 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 3.6 (3H, s, CH ₃), 6.2 (1H, s, CH), 7.6-7.8 (12H, m, ArH)	M ⁺⁺ 996 (28), 190 (100), 152 (48), 146 (76), 104 (61)
6d	2862 (N-O), 1725 (C=O), 1681 (C=O), 640 (C-S-C)	2.6 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.9 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.3 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 6.3 (1H, s, CH), 7.6-7.9 (13H, m, ArH)	M ⁺⁺ 964 (39), 810 (47), 204 (100), 152 (64), 76 (86)
6e	3460 (O-H), 2858 (N-O), 1732 (C=O), 1682 (C=O), 820 (C-H), 668 (C-S-C)	2.7 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.9 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.1 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 5.9 (1H, s, CH), 6.2 (1H, br s, OH), 7.6-7.8 (12H, m, ArH)	M ⁺⁺ 996 (42), 190 (100), 125 (58), 104 (62), 76 (82)
6f	3022 (C-H), 1728 (C=O), 1680 (C=O), 1658 (C=C)	2.5 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.8 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.2 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 3.8 (3H, s, CH ₃), 6.1 (1H, s, CH), 7.6-7.9 (12H, m, ArH)	M ⁺⁺ 1024 (44), 398 (54), 204 (100), 146 (69), 125 (72)
6g	3068 (C-H), 2868 (N-O), 1710 (C=O), 1678 (C=O), 1648 (C=C), 826, 748 (C-H), 656 (C-S-C)	2.4 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.6 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.8 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.2 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 6.2 (1H, s, CH), 7.6-7.9 (13H, m, ArH)	M ⁺⁺ 992 (45), 838 (41), 218 (100), 152 (61), 146 (66)
6h	3462 (O-H), 1708 (C=O), 1678 (C=O), 1638 (C=C), 810 (C-H), 678 (C-S-C)	2.5 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.7 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.9 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.0 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 6.2 (1H, s, CH), 6.5 (1H, br s, OH), 7.6-7.8 (12H, m, ArH)	M ⁺⁺ 1024 (47), 398 (51), 218 (100), 125 (67), 104 (71)
6i	3034 (C-H), 1712 (C=O), 1780 (C=O), 1648 (C=C), 810 (C-H)	2.4 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.7 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.9 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.0 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 6.2 (1H, s, CH), 7.7-7.9 (12H, m, ArH)	M ⁺⁺ 1052 (36), 838 (42), 218 (100), 152 (68), 146 (79)
7a	3460 (O-H), 2872 (N-O), 1708 (C=O), 748, 702 (C-H), 664 (C-S-C)	2.9 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.1 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 7.5-7.8 (13H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, br s, OH)	M ⁺⁺ 1016 (41), 634 (46), 190 (100), 180 (64), 146 (82)
7b	3510 (O-H), 3026 (C-H), 2862 (N-O), 1716 (C=O), 1638 (C=N), 828, 752 (C-H), 648 (C-S-C)	2.8 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.3 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 6.2 (1H, br s, OH), 7.6-7.8 (12H, m, ArH), 8.1 (1H, br s, OH)	M ⁺⁺ 1048 (39), 480 (56), 190 (100), 152 (68), 132 (61)
7c	3506 (O-H), 1712 (C=O), 1656 (C=N), 816, 750 (C-H), 659 (C-S-C)	2.8 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.0 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 3.4 (3H, s, CH ₃), 7.7-7.9 (12H, m, ArH), 8.0 (1H, br s, OH)	M ⁺⁺ 1076 (49), 694 (52), 190 (100), 104 (68), 76 (72)
7d	3540 (O-H), 1712 (C=O), 1636 (C=N), 752, 703 (C-H), 666 (C-S-C)	2.5 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.9 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.1 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 7.6-7.8 (13H, m, ArH), 8.3 (1H, br s, OH)	M ⁺⁺ 1044 (51), 634 (58), 204 (100), 180 (63), 146 (78)

7e	3480 (O-H), 2868 (N-O), 1702 (C=O), 1632 (C=N), 645 (C-S-C)	2.6 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.9 (2H, t, NH ₂), 3.2 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 6.4 (1H, br s, OH), 7.7–7.8 (12H, m, ArH), 8.0 (1H, br s, OH)	M ⁺⁺ 1076 (32), 480 (48), 204 (100), 132 (71), 104 (75)
7f	3472 (O-H), 2860 (N-O), 1708 (C=O), 1628 (C=N), 814 (C-H)	2.4 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.6 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.0 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 3.3 (3H, s, CH ₃), 7.6–7.8 (12H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, br s, OH)	M ⁺⁺ 1104 (46), 694 (52), 204 (100), 180 (62), 146 (72)
7g	3438 (O-H), 2856 (N-O), 1716 (C=O), 1628 (C=N), 748, 700 (C-H), 672 (C-S-C)	2.5 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.6 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.9 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.2 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 7.6–7.9 (13H, m, ArH), 8.3 (1H, br s, OH)	M ⁺⁺ 1072 (41), 634 (55), 218 (100), 152 (70), 146 (76)
7h	3490 (O-H), 2866 (N-O), 1720 (C=O), 1642 (C=N), 824 (C-H), 678 (C-S-C)	2.4 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.7 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.9 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.2 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 6.1 (1H, br s, OH), 7.7–7.9 (12H, m, ArH), 8.0 (1H, br s, OH)	M ⁺⁺ 1104 (38), 480 (52), 218 (100), 180 (59), 146 (75), 76 (82)
7i	3492 (O-H), 2860 (N-O), 1724 (C=O), 1632 (C=N), 829, 748 (C-H), 638 (C-S-C)	2.5 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.6 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.8 (2H, t, NCH ₂), 3.2 (2H, t, OCH ₂), 3.4 (3H, s, CH ₃), 7.7–7.9 (12H, m, ArH), 8.0 (1H, br s, OH)	M ⁺⁺ 1132 (42), 694 (49), 480 (59), 218 (100), 146 (74), 76 (81)
9a	3530 (O-H), 3322 (N-H), 1648 (C=N), 704 (C-H), 650 (C-S-C)	7.1 (1H, s, NH), 7.6–7.9 (9H, m, ArH), 8.1 (1H, br s, OH)	M ⁺⁺ 638 (51), 484 (54), 268 (100), 152, (68)
9b	3468 (O-H), 3382 (N-H), 1652 (C=N), 828, 704 (C-H), 672 (C-S-C)	6.2 (1H, br s, OH), 7.0 (1H, s, NH), 7.6–7.9 (8H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, br s, OH)	M ⁺⁺ 670 (31), 484 (58), 180 (100), 152 (68)
9c	3518 (O-H), 3368 (N-H), 1162 (C-O), 648 (C-S-C)	3.4 (3H, s, CH ₃), 6.9 (1H, s, NH), 7.6–7.9 (8H, m, ArH), 8.3 (1H, br s, OH)	M ⁺⁺ 698 (28), 636 (42), 246 (100), 152 (79)

region 2960–2925 cm⁻¹ and ¹H NMR signal at δ 4.3–4.6 ppm for reactive methylene group disappeared, which were present in **4a-c** and IR band in the region 1658–1638 cm⁻¹ for carbon-carbon double bond and ¹H NMR signal at δ 5.9–6.3 ppm as singlet for methine proton appeared. The carbonyl peak for the alkoxyphthalimide group was still present in the compounds **6a-i**.

Cyclisation of the compounds **6a-i** to *p*-bis-(7-*n*-alkoxyphthalimido-2-hydroxy-4-aryl-6-iminothiazolidino[4,5-*b*]pyrimidin-*N*⁶-yl)biphenyls **7a-i** have been achieved by the reaction of urea in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in acetic acid medium. Formation of thiazolidine condensed pyrimidine ring was confirmed by IR and ¹H NMR spectroscopy. The IR band for carbonyl group and ¹H NMR signal for the proton of C=CHAr group disappeared in thiazolidinopyrimidines and new IR band for OH group in the region of 3540–3430 cm⁻¹ and ¹H NMR signal for the proton of the OH group at δ 8.2–7.9 ppm appeared. The titled compounds **7a-i** were also synthesized by another reaction route in which araldehydes **5a-c** were condensed with **2** at reactive methylene group to give **8a-c**. The compounds **8a-c** were cyclised with urea to furnish **9a-c**, which were condensed with ω-bromoalkoxyphthalimides **3a-c**. The reaction conditions, solvents, bases etc. were similar and

spectral data and chemical tests also confirmed formation of **8a-c** and **9a-c**. Yields were found almost equal in both the processes.

Experimental

Melting points were determined by the electrothermal method in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The IR spectra are recorded in cm⁻¹ and were acquired as potassium bromide pellets on Perkin-Elmer 1800 and Shimadzu 8201 PC FTIR spectrophotometers. The ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker WM-400 spectrophotometer using tetramethylsilane as the internal standard and chemical shifts are expressed in δ (ppm). The mass spectra were recorded on Jeol SX-102 (FAB) mass spectrometer in which *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol was used as matrix. The matrix peaks may appear at *m/z* 136, 137, 154, 289 and 307 in the absence of any metal ion. These peaks, therefore, are recorded on mass spectra. Purity of the synthesized compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel-G and spots were exposed in iodine vapor. In the present investigation, compound **1, 2** and **8a-c** were prepared by reported methods⁵.

General procedure for the synthesis of p-bis-(3-n-alkoxyphthalimido-2-iminothiazolidin-4-one-N²-yl)biphenyls 4a-c :

Singh *et al.* : Synthesis of alkoxyphthalimide derivatives of *p*-bis-(2-hydroxy-4-aryl-6-iminothiazolidino *etc.*

A mixture of *p*-bis-(2-iminothiazolidin-4-one-*N*²-yl)biphenyl **2** (0.02 mol, 7.68 g) and ω -bromoethoxyphthalimide **3a** (0.04 mol, 10.76 g) were taken in 50 ml absolute alcohol. Pyridine (0.08 mol, 4.19 ml) was added as base and it was heated to reflux for 15–16 h. Excess of the solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure. On cooling, crystals started to form gradually in remaining reaction mixture. The crystals were filtered and recrystallised with absolute alcohol. Similar method and appropriate reagents were also used to synthesize the compounds **4a** and **4c**. Physicochemical and spectroscopic data are given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

General procedure for the synthesis of p-bis-(3-n-alkoxyphthalimido-5-arylidene-2-iminothiazolidin-4-one-N²-yl)biphenyls 6a-i :

A mixture of *p*-bis-(3-ethoxyphthalimido-2-iminothiazolidin-4-one-*N*²-yl)biphenyl **4a** (0.01 mol, 7.6 g) and benzaldehyde **5a** (0.02 mol, 1.37 ml) was dissolved in 50 ml glacial acetic acid. In this reaction mixture, anhydrous sodium acetate was added and was refluxed for 10–12 h. Excess of the solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure. The reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice. Crystals were filtered, washed with cold water, dried and recrystallised with absolute alcohol. Compounds **6b-i** were also synthesized by using appropriate reagents and changing in reflux time. The physical and spectroscopic data are given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

General procedure for the synthesis of p-bis-(7-n-alkoxyphthalimido-2-hydroxy-4-aryl-6-iminothiazolidino[4,5-b]pyrimidin-N⁶-yl)biphenyls 7a-i :

A mixture of *p*-bis-(3-ethoxyphthalimido)-5-benzylidene-2-iminothiazolidin-4-one-*N*²-yl)biphenyl **6a** (0.01 mol, 9.36 g) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.02 mol, 1.64 g) was dissolved in 40 ml glacial acetic acid. Urea (0.02 mol, 1.2 g) was added in the reaction mixture and was heated to reflux for 10–12 h. Excess of the solvent was distilled off under reduced-pressure and the mixture was poured on crushed ice after cooling at room temperature. The product was filtered, washed with cold water and

recrystallised with absolute alcohol. Compounds **7b-i** were also synthesized in the similar way by using appropriate reagents. Physical and spectroscopic data of synthesized compounds are given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

General procedure for the synthesis of p-bis-(2-hydroxy-4-aryl-7H-6-iminothiazolidino[4,5-b]pyrimidin-N⁶-yl)biphenyls 9a-c :

p-Bis-(5-benzylidene-2-iminothiazolidin-4-one-*N*²-yl)biphenyl **8a** (0.005 mol, 2.96 g) and urea (0.01 mol, 0.6 g) were dissolved in 50 ml glacial acetic acid. Anhydrous sodium acetate (0.01 mol, 0.82 g) was added and the reaction mixture was heated to reflux for 10–12 h. Excess of the solvent was distilled off and after cooling, the reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice. Product was filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallised from alcohol. Other both the compounds **9b** and **9c** were also synthesized by using appropriate reagents. Physical and spectroscopic data are given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

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